

INTERACTION OF MATRIX CRACKING AND DELAMINATION IN CROSS-PLY LAMINATES: SIMULATIONS WITH STOCHASTIC COHESIVE ZONE ELEMENTS

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SUMMARY

This paper is aimed at the interaction between matrix cracking and delamination in CFRP cross-ply laminates under quasi-static tensile loading. It is studied in finite-element simulations by introducing stochastic cohesive zone elements to account for the effect of microstructural randomness of these laminates on propagation of delamination.

Keywords: Cross-ply laminates; CFRP; matrix cracking; delamination; microstructural randomness; cohesive zone modelling

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced polymer composites (FRPCs) are being increasingly used in structural applications requiring high specific strength and stiffness. The performance of FRPCs is affected by multi-mechanism damage evolution under loading, which in its turn is affected by microstructural stochasticity in the material. This means that the fracture of a FRPC is a stochastic process. However, to date most analyses of these materials have treated them in a deterministic way. In this paper the effect of stochasticity in FRPCs is investigated through the application of cohesive zone elements, accounting for spatially random properties of laminates. Such elements may be termed ‘stochastic cohesive zone elements’ and are used in this paper to investigate the effect of microstructural randomness on the fracture behaviour of cross-ply laminate specimens loaded in tension. It is confirmed that microstructure can significantly affect the macroscopic response of FRPCs, emphasizing the need to account for microstructural randomness in order to make accurate prediction of the performance of composite structures made of such laminates.

Failure in composite structures is often caused by the development of different damage mechanisms initiated locally. Particular damage modes depend upon the type of loading, the lay-up and stacking sequence of the composite. For effective predictive capabilities, all mechanisms of failure must be taken into account. But this should be preceded by a thorough study of single mechanisms and a character of their interaction. In fibre-reinforced laminates, delamination between plies is one of the most common types of damage because of the relatively low interlaminar strengths of such composites. The nature of the delamination process is complex presupposing the use of advanced FE modelling techniques for its analysis. Simulations based on the failure

mechanisms should have the capability of predicting the initiation, size and propagation of delamination. Another important factor affecting this damage mode is the effect of microstructural randomness on the delamination behaviour in FRPC laminates. Most of the analyses of fibre-reinforced composite materials are treated in a deterministic way, i.e. the material is considered as having an ordered (deterministic) distribution of fibres. But in reality, the microstructure of fibre-reinforced composites is far from ordered as the fibres are usually randomly distributed in the matrix.

Wang *et al.* [1] were among the first to consider the location of matrix cracks as a statistical quantity in their models. They presented a stochastic simulation model for the growth of multiple matrix cracks in cross-ply laminates subjected to both static and fatigue loads. Baxevanakis *et al.* [2] demonstrated a high level of spatial non-uniformity in a composite by applying the image analysis technique to cross-sectional areas of T300/914 specimens. Silberschmidt has established that cross-ply carbon-epoxy laminates demonstrate a considerable extent of randomness in distributions of transverse cracks in 90° layers [3] and studied the effect of microstructural randomness on the distribution of matrix cracks in these laminates [4]. Trias *et al.* [5] showed by comparing stress and strain distributions obtained with periodic and random models for a carbon fibre-reinforced polymer that periodic models can be used to assess effective properties but random ones must be considered for simulations of local phenomena such as damage accumulation or matrix cracking.

Thus, previous studies have demonstrated the microscopically random nature of FRPC laminates. This paper emphasizes the fact that this spatial non-uniformity should be directly taken into account while addressing damage scenarios.

DELAMINATION INITIATION FROM TIPS OF MATRIX CRACKS

It is well established that, under the application of uniaxial loading, the early stage of damage in cross-ply $[0_n/90_m/0_n]$ laminates is dominated by transverse matrix cracking in 90° plies. Matrix cracks develop in the fibre direction and extend across the laminates from the free edges of the test specimen. Transverse cracks induce local stress concentration at crack tips and can involve significant interlaminar delamination between 0° and 90° plies, due to the nature of cross-ply laminates [6].

In this work a matrix crack is introduced in the inner 90° layers of the cross-ply laminate $[0_1/90_4/0_1]$, and the processes of initiation and growth of delaminations from the tips of the matrix crack are simulated for a case of tensile loading. The potential path for the delamination growth in cross-ply laminates is the resin-rich area between the 0° and 90° layers. It is represented in finite-element (FE) simulations by cohesive elements to analyze the initiation and development of delamination damage and to obtain the characteristic values of delamination crack length. A value of half scatter of 50% for fracture energy G_{IC} was selected as a starting point to underline the effect of the material's stochastic nature on the course of damage initiation and propagation. This was achieved by introducing random cohesive zone properties in terms of the fracture energy and comparing the obtained results with those for a deterministic case. In the latter, all the cohesive elements have the same fracture energy \overline{G}_{IC} .

Numerical simulations were carried out in order to highlight the effect of varying fracture energy G_{IC} since the ability of a structure to resist defect propagation is

characterized by the fracture toughness of the material. The fracture energy of cohesive elements was considered to be represented by a distribution based on a two-parameter Weibull's probability density function for the chosen scatter width [$G_{IC}^{\min} = 0.5\bar{G}_{IC}$, $G_{IC}^{\max} = 1.5\bar{G}_{IC}$]. Figure 1 shows the effect of a variation in fracture energy on the bilinear traction-separation curves in a cohesive zone model with the values of critical and maximum opening displacement remaining constant. Changing the value of fracture energy from $1.5\bar{G}_{IC}$ to $0.5\bar{G}_{IC}$ also reduces the values of tripping traction and initial stiffness as seen in Fig. 1b.

Fracture along the interface between 0° and 90° plies of the laminate has a mixed-mode nature which needs to be accounted for by the cohesive zone model. The mode-mixity was taken into account by introducing the shear/normal coefficients for maximum stress (traction of the cohesive law) and cohesive energy (fracture energy) into the finite-element model.

Fig. 1 Bilinear traction-separation law (a) (after [7]) and its bounds for variation of fracture energy (b)

A three-dimensional model of $[0_1/90_4/0_1]$ cross-ply laminate was developed in the finite element software MSc Marc. The lay-up of its axial transversal cross-section is shown in Fig. 2 with a matrix crack introduced within the weak 90° layers.

Fig. 2 Cross-ply laminate $[0_1/90_4/0_1]$ with matrix crack under tension

Displacement-controlled analysis was performed by applying displacement at one end of the model and applying constraints at the other.

The developed model had a single matrix crack and cohesive elements between the 0° and 90° layers with random fracture properties based on a 2-parameter Weibull's distribution [8], multiple statistical realizations of those parameters were implemented in our simulations. Figure 3 demonstrates the delamination developing from the matrix crack tip.

Fig. 3 Damage initiation in $[0_1/90_4/0_1]$ laminate from the tip of a matrix crack under tension - a close up

To visualise the delamination area between 0° and 90° plies, Fig. 4 shows the damage level in the cohesive layer of elements with its front also shown. This crack propagation is obtained for a uniform (deterministic) model, i.e. not accounting for the microstructural randomness exhibited by CFRP laminates.

Fig. 4 Damage distribution at the interface

A number of statistical realisations of the distribution of fracture properties over a set of cohesive zone elements were simulated for the random properties based on the Weibull's probability distribution, in addition to a case with uniform fracture properties. The results obtained for evolution of the delamination length as a function of prescribed displacement are shown in Fig. 5.

It can be seen from Fig. 5 that the crack lengths for different random property realisations reveal a wide scatter. Some 70% of the random fracture properties cases demonstrate values of delamination lengths higher than that in the case with uniform (deterministic) properties. These depictions emphasize the need to account for microstructural randomness in analysing FRPCs laminates as this can have a profound effect on damage initiation and propagation.

Fig. 5 Variation in crack length with displacement for different statistical realisations

Conclusions

The damage and failure mechanisms of composites are investigated in this paper by analysing the effect of microstructural randomness on the initiation and development of delamination damage between 0° and 90° layers. The values of delamination crack length demonstrate a large scatter when the fracture energy level for cohesive zone elements is introduced as a random variable based on the Weibull's probability distribution. The results of a number of 3D realizations underlined the need to account for the microstructural randomness since predictions based on the uniform or mean properties data for these laminates could significantly overestimate the critical value of crack lengths.

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